

MINOAS NEWSLETTERS

MINOAS Concept | MINOAS key achievements of the first quarter |

Deliverables

The two first deliverables of the MINOAS project have been completed:

- D1.1-Project handbook
- D1.2–Dissemination and Communication Plan

Milestones

The first milestone of MINOAS has been completed:

- MS1-Availability of CHILON use case definitions (M04)

Papers

The MINOAS project has already published two (2) papers:

- 1 in IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications
- 1 in IEEE Wireless Communication Letters

Patents

The MINOAS project has filled three (3) patents.

Keynotes

The MINOAS project has presented its initial results in the conference ICCDN.

MINOAS Concept

Bringing to fruition the notion of AI-aided B5G optical wireless networks calls for a flexible, scalable, and powerful network information theory approach that will go beyond the limitations of Shannon, a revolutionary ML-based transmission and reception framework that will be supported by cutting edge technology components, and a novel universal resource management methodology, which includes cell-free radio access mechanisms, ML-assisted mobility management and blockage avoidance schemes, AI-based resource and network orchestration. Additionally, MINOAS will identify the critical technology gaps and invent, optimize, and assess the key enablers for the B5G optical wireless networks. In particular, MINOAS approach is built upon three well-defined pillars:

- Pillar I: Beyond Shannon Optical wireless communications for high-data rate, by exploiting mature optical transceivers and novel optical materials as well as cell free access mechanism designs, in order to significantly improve the resource usage by introducing novel strategies for range expansion, supporting of novel use cases and killer apps, and commercializing the underutilized spectrum.

Your opinion matters!

We created the following questionnaires through our LinkedIn Group:

- Optical wireless communications are taking their place in the 6G era, promising to enable a number of extra-ordinary applications, including nano-scale communications that can play a key role on countermeasure a number of diseases, implants in-body out-of-body communications, underwater high-data-rate communications, fronthaul communications, vehicle-to-everything communications, backhaul connectivity (Free space optics-FSO), as well as non-terrestrial and satellite communications. In your opinion, which is the most futuristic applications?

- 50% of the participants answered nanoscale (in-body)
- 25% of the participants went with underwater, and
- 25% of the participants with non-terrestrial communications.

- Pillar II: AI-based optical wireless network orchestration to maximize the system’s energy efficiency, support ultra-high availability and applications with diverse requirements, optimize network topology and management, enable device collaboration, and transform B5G backhaul/midhaul/fronthaul networks into intelligent platforms.
- Pillar III: “Almost-zero latency” and high-computational capabilities at the edge by means of grant-free and semi-grant free access, caching and task offloading to transform the B5G network into a “zero-response” computing platform.

Towards modeling and assessing the disorientation and misalignment effect in optical wireless nano-networks

Abstract: It is true that medical diagnosis and treatment have always been at the top of research activities. Recently, a very promising area that combines the operation of human body with the principles of wireless communications has arisen and given birth to the field of bio-photonics. Although the deployment of nano-networks inside the human body seems to be an achievable goal, the implementation of optical wireless nano-networks remains a very challenging field due to the lack of accurate channel modeling. In this paper, we comprehensively investigate the optical wireless nano-communication channels by considering the deterministic geometric losses (e.g., optical absorption and scattering in human tissues), and modeling the impact of nano-node disorientation and misalignment in in-body nano-networks. To this end, we analytically study the stochastic nature of disorientation and misalignment coefficient in terms of the position and orientation of the nano-node with reference to the out-of-body optical receiver.

This paper will appear in [IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications](#).

Your opinion matters!

- Which do you believe is the key limited factor in optical wireless links?
 - 20% of the participants answered blockage
 - 67% of the participants voted misalignment & disorientation
 - 7% of the participants answered hardware imperfections, and
 - 7% of the participants voted for power limitations

Active questionnaires

The following questionnaire is still active in our LinkedIn Group:

- Which do you think is the order of data rate that a 1 km FSO link can achieve?
 - Mbps
 - Gbps
 - Tbps
 - Pbps

Do not miss the chance to cast your vote.

NeuroRIS: Neuromorphic-Inspired Metasurfaces

Abstract: Conventional reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RIS) are controlled through high-latency field programmable gate array or micro-controller circuits usually implementing artificial neural networks (ANNs) for tuning the RIS phase array that exhibit very high energy requirements. Most importantly, conventional RIS are unable to function under realistic scenarios i.e, high-mobility/low-end user equipment (UE). In this paper, we benefit from the advanced computing power of neuromorphic processors and design a new type of RIS named **NeuroRIS**, to supporting high mobility UEs through real time adaptation to the ever-changing wireless channel conditions. To this end, the neuromorphic processing unit tunes all the RIS meta-elements in the orders of 10^6 for particular switching circuits e.g., varactors while exhibiting significantly low energy requirements since it is based on event-driven processing through spiking neural networks for accurate and efficient phase-shift vector design. Simulations show that the NeuroRIS achieves very close rate performance to a conventional RIS-based on ANNs, while requiring significantly reduced energy consumption.

This paper will appear in [IEEE Wireless Communications Letters](#).

Get in touch with us

- Website: <https://minoas-project.gr/>
- YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/@minoas-project>
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/project-minoas/>
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YouTube Videos

In the first quarter of the project MINOAS, we released nine (9) videos in the MINOAS YouTube channel.

